

Synthesis of some Schiff base complexes of nickel(II) and copper(II) derived from *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde

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Complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with Schiff bases 4-dimethylaminobenzylidene-4-chloroaniline (DABCA)/4-dimethylaminobenzylidene-4-bromoaniline (DABBA)/4-dimethylaminobenzylidene-3-nitroaniline (DABNA) of general formula ML(H₂O)₂Cl₂·2H₂O and MLCl₂(H₂O)₂·2H₂O have been synthesized. Coordination of azomethine nitrogen in the Schiff base to the metal has been proposed. Ligand field parameters of some of the complexes have been calculated.

Schiff base complexes with transition metals have played a prominent role in the development of coordination chemistry¹. Several Schiff base metal complexes have been studied because of their industrial and biological applications^{2,3}. Some organometallic complexes of transition metals derived from substituted anilines have been investigated⁴⁻⁶. The present investigation aims at the study of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with some bioactive ligands (Schiff base) derived from 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and substituted anilines.

Results and discussion

Complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 4-dimethylaminobenzylidene-4-chloroaniline (DABCA) : The analytical results show that metal-to-ligand ratio is 1 : 1 in the complexes (Table 1). The molar conductance values (10⁻³ M in methanol) of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are in accordance with uni-bivalent electrolytic nature and non-electrolytic nature of the complexes, respectively⁷. The diamagnetic nature of the Ni^{II} complex suggests the square-planar geometry. The Cu^{II} complex gives μ_{eff} value 1.91 B.M.

The IR ligand band of the -N(CH₃)₂ group (2830 cm⁻¹) on chelation appears at higher frequencies, i.e. 2860 ± 10 cm⁻¹ in the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. The C-N (due to -N(CH₃)₂ group) band shifts to lower frequency region by 40–50 cm⁻¹ in the complexes⁸⁻¹⁰. The C=N (azomethine) ligand band (1610 cm⁻¹) shifts down by about 40–50 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, indicating the participation of azomethine nitrogen in coordination⁴⁻¹⁰. In the spectra of both the complexes, band at 3400–3500 cm⁻¹ and 770 ± 10 cm⁻¹ are assignable to stretching and rocking mode of coordinated water molecules, respectively. The new bands in the complexes at 500 ± 10 and 430 ± 10 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, respectively. Further a band at 290 cm⁻¹

Table 1. Analytical and physico-chemical data of the complexes*

Compd.	Colour/M.p.°C	Metal% Found/(Calcd.)	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
(DABCA)	Yellow 110	– –	– –	– –
[Ni(DABCA) (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ · 2H ₂ O	Brown 128	11.84 (12.70)	212.0	Diamag.
[Cu(DABCA) Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]. 2H ₂ O	Black 136	13.40 (13.64)	29.60	1.91
(DABBA)	Yellow 85	–	–	–
[Ni(DABBA) Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]. 2H ₂ O	Buff 100	5.88 (5.40)	27.1	3.12
[Cu(DABBA) Cl ₂].H ₂ O	Buff 115	5.68 (5.96)	34.80	1.84
(DABNA)	Orange 120	–	–	–
[Ni(DABNA) (H ₂ O) ₂]. Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Brown 165	11.91 (12.40)	218.3	Diamag.
[Cu(DABNA) Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]. 2H ₂ O	Brown 135	12.80 (13.34)	32.40	1.94

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

in the Cu^{II} complex is probably due to $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ ^{9,10}.

The electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex shows two bands at 12345 and 18180 cm⁻¹, assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g (ν_1) and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{2g} (ν_2) transitions. The third band appears obscured by a strong charge transfer band. This suggests a square-planar geometry. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex gives a broad band which is splitted slightly giving peaks at 12658 and 16393 cm⁻¹ (²E_g → ²T_{2g} transition). The ligand field parameters 10 Dq, λ' and LFSE were

found to be 15148 cm^{-1} , -788 cm^{-1} and $108.97\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The electronic band position and ligand field parameters are in good agreement with the distorted octahedral geometry of the Cu^{II} complex¹¹⁻¹³.

Complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 4-dimethylamino-benzylidene-4-bromoaniline (DABCA) : The results of elemental analyses show that the complexes have 1 : 1, metal-to-ligand ratio (Table 1). The molar conductance values for Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes suggest them to be non-electrolyte⁷. The observed magnetic moment for the Ni^{II} complex is 3.12 B.M. and for Cu^{II} complex is 1.84 B.M.

The IR ligand band of the $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ group (2800 cm^{-1}) on chelation shifts to higher frequency region indicating the participation of this group in chelation⁸. These vibrations have been observed at 2850 cm^{-1} in Ni^{II} complex and at 2860 cm^{-1} in Cu^{II} complex. This is also witnessed by lowering in the C–N (aliphatic) frequency in the spectra of complexes. The sharp band due to $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ (azomethine group) at 1610 cm^{-1} in the spectra of ligand has been shifted to at lower frequency in the metal complexes, i.e. $1570 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating the coordination through the azomethine nitrogen⁵⁻¹⁰. A broad band in the region $3400\text{--}3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in both the complexes indicate the presence of water molecules (stretching mode); however a band at 750 cm^{-1} (rocking) in case of Ni^{II} complex suggest its coordinated nature. Some new bands have been observed due to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ at 560 , 480 and 310 cm^{-1} , respectively in Ni^{II} complex. The bands at 440 and 330 cm^{-1} in Cu^{II} complex have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ ^{9,10}.

The electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex shows bands at 16393 and 17543 cm^{-1} (because of splitting of a peak into two) and a band at 21276 cm^{-1} which have been assigned to ${}^3\text{A}_{2\text{g}}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1\text{g}}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2\text{g}}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1\text{g}}(\text{P})$ transitions respectively. The band due to ${}^3\text{A}_{2\text{g}}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2\text{g}}(\text{F})$ transition, could not be observed. The values of $10 Dq$, B , β , β^0 , λ' and LFSE were calculated¹³ and found to be 9426 cm^{-1} , 643 cm^{-1} , 0.59 , 40.46 , -224 and $135.62\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. Based on these parameters and band positions and magnetic moment value, a distorted octahedral geometry has been suggested. The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complex shows two bands at $12,195$ and 21739 cm^{-1} corresponding to transition ${}^2\text{B}_{1\text{g}} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2\text{g}}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1\text{g}} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_{\text{g}}$, respectively, confirming the square-planar geometry¹¹⁻¹³.

Complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 4-dimethylamino-benzylidene-3-nitroaniline (DABNA) : The elemental analyses indicate that the metal-to-ligand ratio is 1 : 1 for these complexes (Table 1). The molar conductance (in methanol, 10^{-3} M) suggest the uni-bivalent and non-electrolytic nature of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively⁷.

The diamagnetic nature of the Ni^{II} complex suggest the square-planar geometry. The Cu^{II} complex gives μ_{eff} value 1.94 B.M.

The IR band of the $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ group (2820 cm^{-1}) in the ligand shifts higher region ($2845 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$) after chelation. This positive shift suggests coordination through dimethyl amino group⁸⁻¹⁰. A sharp band due to $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ (azomethine group) appears at 1600 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of ligand^{9,10} suffers a red shift on chelation⁵⁻¹⁰ ($1560 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The presence of coordinated water molecules in both the metal complexes have been confirmed by the presence of two IR bands at around 3400 and $770 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to stretching and rocking vibrations respectively^{9,10}. The bands at 510 ± 10 and $400 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibrations. In case of Cu^{II} complex the band due to $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ appears at 310 cm^{-1} ^{9,10}.

The electronic spectrum of diamagnetic Ni^{II} complex shows three bands at 12987 , 17857 and 22727 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^1\text{A}_{1\text{g}} \rightarrow {}^1\text{E}_{\text{g}} (\nu_1)$, ${}^1\text{A}_{1\text{g}} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{2\text{g}} (\nu_2)$ and ${}^1\text{A}_{1\text{g}} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1\text{g}} (\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively, which favours the square-planar geometry¹¹⁻¹³. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex shows two bands at 12048 and 15873 cm^{-1} correspond to an octahedral geometry¹¹⁻¹³. The partial splitting in the band has occurred due to lowering symmetry i.e. D_{4h} (distorted O_h). In octahedral structure the band at $12048\text{--}15873\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (broad) may be ascribed to ${}^1\text{E}_{\text{g}} \rightarrow {}^2\text{T}_{2\text{g}}$ transition. The values of ligand field parameters¹³, $10 Dq$, λ' and LFSE comes to be 14598 cm^{-1} , -717 cm^{-1} and $105.02\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

Experimental

The Schiff bases (DABCA, DABBA and DABNA) were synthesized by refluxing a mixture of an equimolar amount of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with 4-chloroaniline/4-bromoaniline/3-nitroaniline in methanol on a water-bath for 4–5 h. The resulting coloured products were crystallized from methanol.

The metal complexes were prepared by adding a methanolic solution of the metal salt ($\text{MCl}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$) to a methanolic solution of the Schiff base in 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio and refluxing the mixture on a water bath for 4–5 h. The resulting coloured complexes were washed with methanol and petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhyd. CaCl_2 in a desiccator and further in an electric oven at 70° . The purity of the complexes was checked by TLC using silica gel.

The elemental analyses were done at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. M.p. was determined on a Toshniwal CL-0301 apparatus. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-

2B spectrophotometer and IR spectra (KBr) on Perkin-Elmer-577 spectrophotometer at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic moments were measured at room temperature by the Gouy's method. Conductances were measured on an Elico Cm-82 conductivity bridge.

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